

Scenario 3: Slow adoption of technology due to government regulations, lack of interest from educational institutions, or insufficient professor preparedness to adopt new technologies

Adopting technology in higher education in Brazil will occur slowly, significantly influenced by government regulations, institutional interest, resource variability, and professor preparedness. Despite the current adoption of mobile technologies by students and professors, the same is not evident in universities. Emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, 3D Printing, and Robotics, although already present in colleges in various countries, will not be as prevalent in Brazilian classrooms throughout the teaching and learning process. The limited presence of these technologies in classrooms reflects the complexity and diversity of opinions in the Brazilian educational landscape and socioeconomic inequalities in access to and quality of education.

For such technologies to be integrated into Higher Education, professors should receive training to handle these tools and thus impart knowledge to students. Within this hypothetical scenario, this does not occur. Furthermore, the lack of adequate training for educators impedes the effective use of technologies such as Artificial Intelligence for personalized learning despite recognition of the evolving role of the professor in this context. Since the mentioned technologies lack widespread adoption by Brazilian higher education, the professor's figure as a source of knowledge prevails, and autonomous learning faces more difficulty asserting itself.

These issues indicate a possible deterioration in the quality of education, exacerbated by outdated education, lack of personalization and innovation, and a growing disconnect with the needs of the job market. Compared to educational institutions in other countries that keep pace with technological advancements and apply them in their teaching methodology, this deterioration occurs in Brazil. Students relying solely on institutional learning will become increasingly outdated.

The problem of slow adoption of new technologies may stem from the interests of large economic groups, which prefer to offer inexpensive education to attract as many students as

possible without necessarily focusing on the quality of education. With this low quality of education, students realize that they are inadequately prepared to enter the job market or have outdated knowledge, since with technological revolution and globalization, the world is constantly evolving and very quickly, leading to cases where, despite graduating, the student cannot secure their first internship or job, causing depression and other mental disorders that may increase dropout rates from higher education courses, as the job market does not see value in what the student is learning. The student ends up interpreting that the market does not value them as human beings.

According to the theory of disruption, technical courses and other short-term course modalities will continue to improve to the point of threatening the university market and traditional teaching models of 4 years or more so that training completed in up to 2 years becomes more interesting and attractive due to the slow adoption of technology by traditional higher education institutions.

Changes in the use of infrastructure in higher education institutions will be inevitable, as the trend is for learning resources to be available wherever the student is. Whenever they desire, and slow technology adoption will hinder this aspect, as learning will be a collaborative activity, classes will be designed to be learning guides, in a collaborative yet individualized task where the student seeks learning in the way they prefer, collaboration will be remote or face-to-face, with the latter option being unfeasible if there is no rapid adoption of resources in institutions, as it will be continuous and enabled by technology, and institutional spaces will be geared towards this type of collaboration, outsourcing non-strategic services that are not essential institutional capabilities.

Researchers will control instruments and collect data from their offices or laboratories that will not necessarily be on the premises of the institutions, with the university being a partner in the incubation of innovative businesses and promoting adaptation of higher education courses to academic and market-oriented profiles, with the student now being the protagonist in their education and able to choose a more market-oriented training. Since technology is a constantly changing and evolving factor crucial for the continuity and evolution of a business or enterprise,

there needs to be rapid technological adoption in universities as new demands arise to keep up with the job market. To keep up with rapid technological changes and evolutions and to maintain the balance between innovation and quality of education, a holistic and inclusive approach to technology adoption in universities is crucial.

Career guidance throughout high school will be significantly impacted, as nowadays, with the new high school system, students have a subject called “life project” that benefits from the use of technology to demonstrate how professionals from various fields work and what their day-to-day life is like, without the need to physically go to their workplace, yet with the same quality and clarity, even if only in the classroom, since using technological resources, a student can see themselves in various workplaces, such as with the adoption of virtual reality glasses, which while without them, would require going to places that are often far from school and considering the school year and the number of resources required, it would be impossible to cover a vast range of professions.